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“HARVEST OF EXPERIENCES”

Come where the morning smells like rain,
And sunshine streams full on grain,
Where silent mountains to the westward rise,
Guarding stories of the land.

And here is slow life, but such is true.
In each drop of dew and leaf,
Where tourists tread the pathways clean.

Barefoot days and golden corn.
Once soft hands now know how to sew.
To touch the earth, to make things grow,
To know the art of the farmer-
A work of the heart and will.

The cock of cocks disturbs the night.
Receiving day with amber light,
As baskets fill with so sweet fruits,
Patiently, sweetly, made rewards.

Laughter rings in the air,
As foreigners get acquainted there,
In common feasts, in tales recounted,
In simple lives, both young and old.

Better than travel, better than stay,
It is living life like the bums,
An intermediate between the present and the past,
A plow of every plow a promise.

So go and walk, so go and view.
Our humanity has its roots,

In the soft arms of farm tourism--
You do not visit. You discover your home.

